

Behind the scenes – genuine animal protection and species conservation by EAZA member zoos

Zoos around the world are, in theory (!) venues for nature conservation, education, and educational entertainment. However, few people know what really goes on behind the scenes.

EAZA and professionalism

The European Association of Zoos and Aquariums (EAZA) estimates that **3,000 to 5,000 healthy animals are euthanized** in EAZA member zoos every year for “management reasons” – that is, **not due to illness, but due to genetic reasons or lack of space**. This practice also affects charismatic species such as giraffes, hippos, lions, zebras or various forms of cercopithecus. ([How many healthy animals do zoos put down? - BBC News](#)).

"Directed/management euthanasia" based on the principle of "breed and cull" (which personally reminds me very much of the horrors of World War II, known as the Shoah or Holocaust), whereby genetically fewer valuable individuals are euthanized, is inhumane, unethical and unacceptable.

American zoos, on the other hand, **prefer to regulate reproduction through contraception**, and resort to euthanasia if the individual's health condition no longer allows for any other alternative. For example, in 2024, one African and one Asian elephant were euthanized at the Maryland Zoo and the National Zoo due to their old age, just as in 2013, a polar bear was euthanized at the Central Park Zoo due to an inoperable tumour. In 2010, a sea lion was euthanized at the Oklahoma City Zoo due to lung cancer, or in 2008, a 55-year-old female western lowland gorilla at the Dallas Zoo, also with an inoperable tumour ([List of animals culled in zoos - Wikipedia](#)).

The question is therefore not only biological, but also deeply moral: is it justified to kill a life simply because there is “no space” or “it is not valuable enough from a genetic point of view”? Zoos are not only scientific institutions (I note that very few zoos today conduct scientific activities of appreciable quality and documentation), but also community spaces where the **expectations and values of society are reflected**. We also express this in our statement entitled [Statement - 12 baboons – like a jury – testify against our civilization](#).

The use of appropriate contraception, as seen in the American model, could reduce unnecessary reproduction. However, **EAZA** is apparently **unable to handle this at an appropriate professional level**. This is reflected in the case of the 12 Guinea baboons shot in the **Nuremberg Zoo**, the pregnancies of females despite contraceptive implants inserted into female mandrills in the Kecskemét Wildlife Park, or the over-breeding and inbred population of Hamadryas baboons in the **Nyíregyháza Zoo**, which the Zoo has been able to successfully manage for the time being by transferring a small group each to the Gyöngyös Zoo and the Felsőlajos Private Zoo. However, such host zoos will run out sooner or later. A more competent professional approach would be to **vasectomize** male individuals to prevent over-breeding and inbreeding, rather than to produce offspring that attract visitors but later become unnecessary.

*Based on the last public report of EAZA, issued in August 2021 ([Hamadryas baboon EEP » EAZA](#)) Hamadryas baboon EEP had **948** animals in **37** institutions. „The Hamadryas baboon does not have any specific conservation roles. Rather the Hamadryas baboon population is managed as EEP to maintain and ideally decrease population size and to avoid space competition with **Guinea baboons and other species with important conservation roles**. In order to further improve the welfare of the Hamadryas baboons the EEP is increasing group sizes and reducing the number of institutions that hold smaller groups sizes.” ([Hamadryas](#)*

[baboon EEP » EAZA](#)). This statement is completely contrary to the practice when, for example, Nyíregyháza Zoo transfers mini groups of 3-6 individuals to Gyöngyös Zoo and Felsőljás Private Zoo, while at the same time 12 Guinea baboons are released in Nuremberg. **The system and species coordination are completely dysfunctional and amateurish.**

As I wrote above, in Europe, it is estimated that between 3,000 and 5,000 healthy animals are euthanized annually in zoos ([How many healthy animals do zoos put down? - BBC News](#)).

At least 5 giraffes were euthanized between 2012 and 2014, all in Denmark. 4 hippos in 2012 (Portugal, Spain, Germany, Denmark), 22 zebras and 11 Arabian oryx in several European cities between 2000 and 2012 ([How many healthy animals do zoos put down? - BBC News](#)).

It is a fact that most euthanized animals are not "charismatic" species, but rather rodents or small mammals, although from an ethical point of view there should not necessarily be a difference between life and life. (E.g. a Guinea or African giant rat – ca. 800 gr – in the **HeroRATs program at APOPO** saves hundreds of lives from landmines and identifies the TB samples of thousands of people with 100% accuracy ([HeroRATs](#)). But it's "just" a rodent. Is that why it's worthless?

The clarity of the data is obscured by the fact that zoos do not always clearly document the reason for euthanasia (they cosmeticize the statistics), and in some cases it is indeed difficult to decide whether the euthanasia was for medical or management purposes.

The most extreme cases

The latest scandal, which has caused a stir worldwide, happened just a few days ago, when **Nuremberg Zoo** slaughtered 12 healthy Guinea baboons in July 2025, citing lack of space and failed contraception ([German zoo kills 12 baboons due to overcrowding | blooloop](#) and [Tiergarten Nürnberg: 12 Paviane getötet! Aktivisten stürmen Gelände | Regional | BILD.de](#) and [German zoo kills 12 baboons that it didn't have enough space to house, despite protests | CNN](#) and [German zoo kills 12 healthy baboons that it didn't have space to house](#)). In 2024, the zoo "dropped" the possibility of "directed/management euthanasia" of the animals, as the baboon enclosure could no longer handle the number of individuals and due to the lack of space, a continuous conflict situation developed between the individuals.

The Nuremberg Zoo allegedly tried to find a place for the animals but could not find a host zoo. I can imagine that this is what happened, as well as the fact that the Zoo did **not ask for external help from any civil society organization or smaller non-EAZA member zoos or primate sanctuaries**, because it is quite certain that the placement of the 12 individuals could have been solved, especially with prior preparation. At most, they could have arranged for the baboons to be placed not in one, but in two trips. (I know of shelters and zoos in Hungary, Austria, Great Britain or the Baltics, where, if the 12 individuals had been separated to 2-3 groups, there would certainly have been room for them.) Slaughter was the easiest solution.

*EAZA member zoos are not particularly good at keeping **baboons**, knowing their behaviour and managing conflicts, as I have personally experienced in several places. Wounds and injuries resulting from conflicts often go untreated, the quality of life of animals at the bottom of the hierarchy is quite poor, and since they **constitute the "commercial" and "unwanted" exhibited animals of zoos** (respect for the exception zoos), their feeding is also handled with "careless elegance" in most zoos. (The individual attention and commitment of conscientious caretakers, zookeepers to show them is a different matter.)*

Germany is also a leader in solutions similar to Nuremberg, as 3 Siberian tiger cubs were euthanized at **Magdeburg Zoo** in 2010 because they were hybrids ([List of animals culled in zoos - Wikipedia](#)). Also recent news is that in August 2025, the **Leipzig Zoo** euthanized 3 Siberian tiger cubs because the mother animal did not take care of her cubs, they became weak, and the zoo - to put it simply - did not want to bother and try to raise them by hand, then integrate them ([Zoo Leipzig schläfert drei Tigerbabys ein | FAZ](#) and [Shortly After Birth: Leipzig Zoo Euthanizes Three Tiger Cubs](#) and [Trois bébés tigres de Sibérie délaissés par leur mère, euthanasiés dans un zoo](#)

[allemand - Le Parisien](#) and [Telex: Csak pár napja születtek, mégis el kellett altatni három kistigrist a lipcsei állatkertben](#)). The zoo believed they had no chance of survival.

*I would like to ask one thing, not only from **Leipzig Zoo**, but also from **Budapest Zoo**! In the latter, 2 Sumatran orangutans, the male Chuij and his daughter Moira, died in 2024 ([Index - Belföld - Váratlanul elpusztult két orangután a Fővárosi Állatkertben](#) and [Tragédia a Fővárosi Állatkertben: két emberszabású is elpusztult idén nyáron](#)). The public has not yet received an answer to the cause of the deaths! Zoos work with animals kept in captivity, where **the caretakers are in contact with the animals entrusted to them every day. How is it possible not to notice in time if there is a problem and intervene and act appropriately in time?***

Wellington Zoo in New Zealand announced on 23 February 2019 that it had been forced to euthanise 4 male Hamadryas baboons after the group's social structure collapsed, seriously compromising the animals' welfare.

Severe fighting between the baboons had caused injuries and high levels of distress. As the situation could not be managed, Dr Ngaio Beausoleil, a member of the zoo's animal welfare committee, said euthanasia was the most humane option. Relocation of the baboons was reportedly considered, but neither option was found to improve the animals' condition. Wellington Zoo is a member of the **Zoo and Aquarium Association Australasia** and the **World Association of Zoos and Aquariums** ([Wellington Zoo makes difficult decision for Baboons | Wellington Zoo](#)).

This case once again highlights how unprepared the zoo profession is for keeping animals with complex behavioural systems and sociometry, and how unwilling it is to further develop its knowledge!

In the field of the use of "controlled euthanasia", the "enlightened" and welfare Denmark leads the way...

In the summer of 2025, **Aalborg Zoo** asked its followers for bored pets to feed to its predators, and it never occurred to them that the request was tasteless and unethical ([Aalborg Zoo asks for unwanted pets to feed its predators](#) and [Zoo in Denmark calls for unwanted pets to feed its animals](#)). The situation is different when, despite the otherwise very expensive entrance ticket of 249 DKK (approx. 33.5 EUR), the zoo asks visitors to donate any unnecessary or expired meat products in the freezer to the zoo. However, the zoo has encouraged the public to donate their unwanted pets (e.g. chickens, rabbits, guinea pigs), which they will professionally and "gently" euthanize and feed to predators (e.g. lions, lynxes). Aalborg Zoo has previously asked for horses on its website, with certain health conditions and a maximum height of 150 cm, for which donors can also receive a tax deduction.

The initiative sparked heated debate and ethical objections on social media, so the institution (Aalborg Zoo) – as a way of dealing with the problem, like the socially indignant handling of the Nuremberg Zoo's baboon massacre – **closed the comment section and called on the public to communicate respectfully.**

A similar incident occurred in 2004 at the **Copenhagen Zoo**, also in Denmark. Marius was a male giraffe living at Copenhagen Zoo. Though healthy, he was genetically unsuitable for future captive breeding, as his genes were over-represented in the captive population, so the zoo authorities decided to euthanize him ([Marius the giraffe killed at Copenhagen zoo despite worldwide protests | Animals | The Guardian](#)). The killing of Marius, the young, 2-year-old giraffe, has sparked worldwide protests. **His decapitated body was publicly dissected, in front of children and adults, and his flesh was then fed to lions.**

An online petition to save Marius garnered over 27,000 signatures, several zoos, including Yorkshire Wildlife Park and Budapest Zoo, offered to take him in, and a private individual offered 50,000 euros for Marius, but the zoo did not respond to these offers. After the "fake reasons", **the quintessence of the matter was that this zoo director was awarded the title of honorary citizen of Copenhagen.**

Also, **Copenhagen Zoo** has already destroyed 3 wolves in 2020 to make place for a playground area. In 2014, it killed 4 lions, including two cubs, to make place for a new animal. And in 2012, it killed 2 leopard cubs (genes were over-represented) ([List of animals culled in zoos - Wikipedia](#)).

EAZA zoos have numerous objections to the justified use of "management euthanasia", which they included in a statement in the spring of 2023 with a self-excusing and self-justifying, but unethical attitude:

[2023 04 EAZA Management Euthanasia Culling Statement 4779d7a058.pdf](#).

This also provides a reason, justification, and excuse for member zoos not to speak out against each other, because based on the principle of "today you, tomorrow me" being the "guilty" or "attacked party", there is a sense of isolation and positional fear among them.

The sole purpose of euthanasia is to end the suffering of an animal when there is no other realistic option. Its use is permitted when recommended by a veterinarian; the animal is experiencing stress or conflict that cannot be resolved; it poses a danger to humans; the animal is too old or seriously injured; or there is no suitable placement option ([The Moral and Welfare Issues of Euthanasia | Wild Welfare](#)). **This last clause leaves a "loophole" open, allowing serious abuses and offering zoos the easiest solution without consequences!**

Fortunately, not all countries allow euthanasia, except when the animal poses a threat to human life. A **good/bad example** of this is the shooting of a western lowland gorilla at the **Cincinnati Zoo**. On May 28, 2016, a three-year-old boy entered the gorilla enclosure, where he was grabbed and dragged by the silverback Harambe. Zoo staff were unable to "call" the gorilla in (although the rules forbid it, they didn't dare go in to get the child) and, fearing that the boy's life was in danger, they shot the perfectly healthy Harambe. The video of the incident was widely circulated and became a topic of debate, especially regarding the shooting with a live gun ([Why We Fight for Nonhuman Rights: Harambe's Story | Nonhuman Rights Project](#)). **This could have been avoided if the caretaker and animal had developed a good quality relationship.** (It is unfortunate that in this case, a person who, by his own admission, would do it again in a similar situation, was allowed to remain as director of the zoo.)

There are also examples of questionable euthanasia in Scotland and England. In 2023, the **Camperdown Wildlife Centre** euthanized 4 wolves due to agitation after the death of a pack leader. **Paignton Zoo** euthanized 7 peacocks in 2007 due to complaints from neighbours about noise. A **special case** occurred in 2000 at **Woburn Safari Park**, where 215 Rhesus macaques were euthanized because the group was diagnosed with being infected by the Herpes B virus ([List of animals culled in zoos - Wikipedia](#)).

The B virus or **Herpes B virus** (Cercopithecine Herpesvirus 1) occurs in macaque monkeys and, as a zoonosis, can be transmitted from monkeys to humans. The virus can be spread by a monkey's bite, scratch, or even by secretions or body fluids (e.g., contact of damaged skin tissue with infected body fluids; by body fluids getting into the eyes, nose, or mouth, or by infected instruments: needles, cages).

Herpes B virus can cause encephalomyelitis in humans, which, if left untreated, can lead to severe brain damage (residual neurological symptoms), and although transmission to humans is rare, the mortality rate is 70-80% ([Questioning the Extreme Neurovirulence of Monkey B Virus \(Macacine alphaherpesvirus 1\) - PMC](#) and [About B Virus | B Virus | CDC](#)). Macaques are usually "only" virus carriers.

„Macaques are mainly infected by herpes B virus during adolescence. Macaques under 1 year of age can be infected through close contact with infected mothers. Because they are socially and reproductively active in the prepubescent and pubertal period (2-4 years of age), the chance of infection increases markedly for macaques and baboons. Adult macaques over 2.5 years of age are nearly 100% positive for herpes B virus antibodies in wild populations.“ ([Herpes B virus: History, zoonotic potential, and public health implications | Biosafety and Health](#))

The virus is detected by PCR test or virus cultivation (in a high-security laboratory), and serological tests (ELISA, immunoassay) can distinguish Herpes B from other herpes viruses, so screening of monkeys – along complicated logistics – is possible.

However, there is no vaccine against the Herpes B virus, the only protection against infection is prevention, avoiding scratching and biting, and adhering to strict protocols. Infected individuals could only be handled by caretakers wearing protective clothing, goggles, and gloves, and all visitors contact with the monkeys and the risk of escape should have been prevented. Although I personally do not agree with the destruction of the entire herd in the event of the presence of any virus (not even in the case of the Hungarian foot-and-mouth disease epidemic, which affected the dairy cattle herd in Győr-Moson-Sopron county in 2025), until it is confirmed that all individuals are infected, **I do not consider the Zoo's decision to be attackable due to the high risks in the case of the Herpes B virus.**

In Switzerland, **Basel Zoo** euthanized a newborn orangutan in 2022 because the Zoo did not wish to hand rear the infant after its mother's death. **Bern Zoo** euthanized 2 Namibian lion cubs in 2007 due to insufficient space ([List of animals culled in zoos - Wikipedia](#)).

A story with a happy twist

Helsinki Zoo in Finland originally planned to euthanize its 14-person baboon population. The Finns launched a petition against the plan. A petition to save the Hamadryas baboons at **Helsinki's Korkeasaari Zoo** was initiated in 2004 due to plans to replace them with animals more suited to the Finnish climate. The zoo initially considered euthanizing the baboons, but a public outcry, and the intervention of animal welfare organizations like Animalia, led to a reprieve and temporary housing during enclosure repairs ([Helsinki Zoo to Keep Baboons | Yle](#)). The repairs needed to keep it in good condition were financed by an inheritance of over 640,000 euros. ([World Briefing | Europe: Finland: Public Outcry Saves Baboons - The New York Times](#)).

"Lessons Learned"

The main role of zoos is in principle aimed at species conservation, but this does not mean that they can become a "factory" of nature, where the value of life can be measured and thrown away. **The life of every animal matter, and society has the right to know what is happening behind the scenes.** It would be important for zoos and WAZA, EAZA-type umbrella organizations to understand that the fundamental ethical question is not whether healthy animals can be euthanized – but whether it is allowed?!

American zoos have already stepped up and frequently and successfully use contraception to avoid unnecessary reproduction. In Europe, however, the principle of "breed and cull" is still widespread. And because of successful breeding programs and public-attracting PR, more species are becoming "surplus".

The case of the 12 Nuremberg baboons is a key phenomenon of the future in the discussed problem area, in which – similarly to the other cases presented – **it is not the act but the criticism that disturbs the zoo, and the police do not investigate the killing of the animals, but the outrage of the people.** This represents a complete overturning of the value system.

Of course, I condemn "death threats", but at the same time, let us be aware that behind these "threats" moral accountability will also be pursued. This trend is very bad! If someone had really wanted to hurt, for example, the unethical director and decision-makers of the Nuremberg Zoo, they would not have written messages but would have already acted.

All these cases, actions devoid of any morality in zoos, project the sad fact that the ZooShield Protocol ([ZooShield Protocol – Global Zoo Evacuation Strategy under Polycrisis Conditions](#) and [ZooShield Protocol: Evacuation Destination Countries and Regions](#)), which is freely available (open access) and downloadable for all zoos, falls on deaf ears in the zoo industry, among those people who “warm their chairs” in decision-making positions, and **the real solutions will be realized in open, civil-based, decentralized rescues and resistance in our civilization that will collapse within a decade or two**. In a morally destroyed society, to which zoos have also added their "dirt", this remains the only viable path.

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